

**SOLUTION OF A SYSTEM OF LINEAR ALGEBRAIC EQUATIONS
USING THE SQUARE ROOT METHOD AND DEVELOPMENT OF
SOFTWARE**

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Annotation

There are various methods for solving a system of linear algebraic equations. This article presents the square root method for solving a system of linear algebraic equations, examples are worked out and software is developed for this method.

Keywords: Matrix, system of linear algebraic equations, square root method.

**CHIZIQLI ALGEBRAIK TENGLAMALAR SISTEMASINI KVADRAT
ILDIZLAR USULI BILAN YECHISH VA DASTURIY TA'MINOTINI
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Annotatsiya

Chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasini yechishning turli xil usullari mavjud. Ushbu maqolada chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasini yechishning kvadrat ildizlar usuli keltirilgan, shu usulda misollar ishlab ko`rsatilgan va dasturiy ta`minotlari ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so`zlar: *Matritsa, chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi, kvadrat ildizlar usuli.*

РЕШЕНИЕ СИСТЕМЫ ЛИНЕЙНЫХ АЛГЕБРАИЧЕСКИХ УРАВНЕНИЙ МЕТОДОМ КВАДРАТНОГО КОРНЯ И РАЗРАБОТКА ПРОГРАММНОГО ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ

Аннотация

Существуют различные методы решения систем линейных алгебраических уравнений. В данной статье представлен метод квадратных корней для решения систем линейных алгебраических уравнений (СЛАУ), приведены примеры для этого метода и разработано программное обеспечение.

Ключевые слова: *Матрица, система линейных алгебраических уравнений, метод квадратных корней.*

Texnik yo`nalishlar talabalariga matematik fanlar mavzularini o`tishda dasturiy ta`minotlar va dasturlardan foydalanishga e`tibor qaratish o`tilgan mavzuni o`zlashtirishni osonlashtiradi, talabalarning mavzuga nisbatan

qiziqishlarini orttiradi, shu bilan birga dars samaradorligi sezilarli darajada oshadi.

Chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasini yechishning keng tarqalgan usullaridan biri kvadrat ildizlar usulidir. Bu usulni Xoletskiy usuli deb ham yuritiladi. Bu usul chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasining yechimini topishning aniq usuli hisoblanadi va bu usulda o'zgaruvchilarning aniq qiymatlari topiladi. Bu usul simmetrik shakldagi musbat aniqlangan matritsali chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasini yechish uchun qulay usul hisoblanadi. Matritsaning simmetrikligi chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasini dasturiy vositalardan foydalanib yechishda qulay hisoblanadi.

Aytaylik $A * X = B$ sistema kvadrat ildizlar usuli qo'llanilishi shartlarini bajarsin, u holda shunday S yuqori uchburchak matritsa mavjudki

$$S^T * S = A \quad (4)$$

bo'ladi.

$A * X = B \Rightarrow (S^T * S) * X = B \Rightarrow S^T * (S * X) = B$ ko'rinishda yozish mumkin. Agar $S * X = Y$ deb belgilash kiritsak, u holda X yechimni topish algoritmi quyidagicha ko'rinishni oladi:

- 1) $S^T * S = A$ tenglamadan S -matritsa elementlarini topamiz.
- 2) $S^T * Y = B$ tenglamadan Y -ustun matritsa (vektor) elementlarini topamiz.
- 3) $S * X = Y$ tenglamadan esa X -ustun matritsa, ya'ni yechimni topamiz.

Yuqorida keltirilgan algoritmda faqatgina birinchi bosqich ko'p mehnat talab qiladi. Masalan A matritsa 3×3 matritsa bo'lsa, u holda S matritsani topish formulalarini keltiramiz, keyin umumiy holga o'tamiz:

$$S = \begin{pmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{13} \\ 0 & S_{22} & S_{23} \\ 0 & 0 & S_{33} \end{pmatrix}, S^T = \begin{pmatrix} S_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & 0 \\ S_{13} & S_{23} & S_{33} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$S^T * S = A$$

$$S^T * S = A = \begin{pmatrix} S_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & 0 \\ S_{13} & S_{23} & S_{33} \end{pmatrix} * \begin{pmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{13} \\ 0 & S_{22} & S_{23} \\ 0 & 0 & S_{33} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} S_{11}^2 & S_{11} * S_{12} & S_{13} * S_{11} \\ S_{12} * S_{11} & S_{11}^2 + S_{22}^2 & S_{13} * S_{12} + S_{23} * S_{12} \\ S_{13} * S_{11} & S_{13} * S_{12} + S_{23} * S_{12} & S_{13}^2 + S_{23}^2 + S_{33}^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Umumiy holatda

$$S_{11} = \sqrt{a_{11}}, S_{1i} = \frac{a_{1i}}{S_{11}}, i = 2, \dots, n \text{ va hokazo.}$$

$$S_{ii} = \sqrt{a_{ii} - \sum_{k=1}^{i-1} S_{ki}^2}, S_{ij} = \frac{1}{S_{ii}} (a_{ij} - \sum_{k=1}^{i-1} S_{ki} * S_{kj})$$

Ushbu formula orqali S matritsani topiladi.

Ushbu usulni simmetrik bo'lmagan va musbat aniqlanmagan A matritsali chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi uchun ham qo'llash mumkin. Buning uchun usulni qo'llashdan oldin (3) chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasini chapdan A^T matritsaga ko'paytirish kifoya

$A * X = B \Rightarrow A^T * A * X = A^T * B$ natijada (3) ga ekvivalent bo'lgan sistemaga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\bar{A} * X = \bar{B} \quad (5)$$

bunda $\bar{A} = A^T * A, \bar{B} = A^T * B$ bo'lib, \bar{A} – matritsa simmetrik va musbat aniqlangan bo'ladi, natijada kvadrat ildiz usulidan foydalansak bo'ladi. (3) dan (5) ga o'tish sistemani simmetrizatsiyalash hisoblanadi.

Uch o'zgaruvchili chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi uchun kvadrat ildizlar usulida ildiz topilsin.

$$\begin{cases} 5x - 7y + 8z = 32 \\ 8x - 5y + 4z = 34 \\ -7x + 8y - 5z = -7 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi ni yechish talab qilingan bo'lsin, quyidagicha belgilashlar kiritamiz:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 5 & -7 & 8 \\ 8 & -5 & 4 \\ -7 & 8 & -5 \end{pmatrix}, B = \begin{pmatrix} 32 \\ 34 \\ -7 \end{pmatrix}, X = \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

u holda (1) ni quyidagicha

$$A * X = B \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{A} = A^T * A &= \begin{pmatrix} 5 & 8 & -7 \\ -7 & -5 & 8 \\ 8 & 4 & -5 \end{pmatrix} * \begin{pmatrix} 5 & -7 & 8 \\ 8 & -5 & 4 \\ -7 & 8 & -5 \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} 25 + 64 + 49 & -35 - 40 - 56 & 40 + 32 + 35 \\ -35 - 40 - 56 & 49 + 25 + 64 & -56 - 20 - 40 \\ 40 + 32 + 35 & -56 - 20 - 40 & 64 + 16 + 25 \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} 138 & -131 & 107 \\ -131 & 138 & -116 \\ 107 & -116 & 105 \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{B} = A^T * B &= \begin{pmatrix} 5 & 8 & -7 \\ -7 & -5 & 8 \\ 8 & 4 & -5 \end{pmatrix} * \begin{pmatrix} 32 \\ 34 \\ -7 \end{pmatrix} = \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} 5 * 32 + 8 * 34 + 7 * 7 \\ -7 * 32 - 5 * 34 - 8 * 7 \\ 8 * 32 + 4 * 34 + 7 * 5 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 481 \\ -450 \\ 427 \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

S matritsani elementlarini topamiz:

$$S^T * S = \bar{A}$$

$$S_{11} = \sqrt{a_{11}} = \sqrt{138} = 11.7473$$

$$S_{12} = \frac{a_{12}}{S_{11}} = \frac{-131}{11.7473} = -11.1514$$

$$S_{13} = \frac{a_{13}}{S_{11}} = \frac{107}{11.7473} = 9.1084$$

$$S_{22} = \sqrt{a_{22} - \sum_{k=1}^1 S_{k2}^2} = \sqrt{a_{22} - S_{12}^2} = \sqrt{138 - 11.1514^2} = 3.694$$

$$S_{23} = \frac{1}{S_{22}} (a_{23} - \sum_{k=1}^1 S_{k2} * S_{k3}) = \frac{1}{3.694} (-116 + 11.1514 * 9.1084) = 3.905$$

$$S_{33} = \sqrt{a_{33} - \sum_{k=1}^2 S_{k3}^2} = \sqrt{a_{33} - (S_{13}^2 + S_{23}^2)} = \sqrt{105 - (9.1084^2 + 3.905^2)}$$

$$= 2.605$$

$$\text{Natijada } S = \begin{pmatrix} 11.7473 & -11.1514 & 9.1084 \\ 0 & 3.694 & -3.905 \\ 0 & 0 & 2.605 \end{pmatrix}$$

U holda

$$S^T * Y = \bar{B}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} 11.7473 & 0 & 0 \\ -11.1514 & 3.694 & 0 \\ 9.1084 & -3.905 & 2.605 \end{pmatrix} * \begin{pmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 481 \\ -450 \\ 427 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$1) 11.7473 * y_1 = 481, y_1 = 40.9455$$

$$2) -11.1514 * y_1 + 3.694 * y_2 = -450$$

$$y_2 = \frac{-450 + 11.1514 * y_1}{3.694} = 1.6646$$

$$3) 9.1084 * y_1 - 3.905 * y_2 + 2.605 * y_3 = 427$$

$$y_3 = \frac{427 - 9.1084 * y_1 + 3.905 * y_2}{2.605} = 23.2446$$

$$Y = \begin{pmatrix} 40.9455 \\ 1.6646 \\ 23.2446 \end{pmatrix}$$

Endi X ning yechimlarini topamiz:

$$S * X = Y$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} 11.7473 & -11.1514 & 9.1084 \\ 0 & 3.694 & -3.905 \\ 0 & 0 & 2.605 \end{pmatrix} * \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 40.9455 \\ 1.6646 \\ 23.2446 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$1) 2.605 * z = 23.2446, z = 9$$

$$2) 3.694 * y - 3.905 * z = 1.6646$$

$$y = \frac{1.6646 + 3.905 * z}{3.694} = 10$$

$$3) 11.7473 * x - 11.1514 * y + 9.1084 * z = 40.9455$$

$$x = \frac{40.9455 + 11.1514 * y + 9.1084 * z}{11.7473} = 6$$

Demak, ushbu tenglamaning yechimlari

$$x = \begin{pmatrix} 6 \\ 10 \\ 9 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Ushbu misolni yuqoridagi usulda yechib beruvchi dastur yaratildi, undagi natijani keltirilgan misol natijasi bilan taqqoslaymiz va natija bir xilligini ko`ramiz:

```
import numpy as np

# === 1. Kiritish qismi ===
n = int(input("O'zgaruvchilar sonini kiriting (n): "))

print("\nA matritsa koeffitsiyentlarini kiriting (har bir satr alohida, elementlar
orasiga bo'shliq qo'ying):")
A = np.zeros((n, n))
for i in range(n):
    A[i] = list(map(float, input(f"{i+1}-satr: ").split()))

print("\nOzod hadlarni kiriting (B vektor):")
b = np.array(list(map(float, input("B = ").split())))

# === 2. Simmetrizatsiya (A^T * A va A^T * b) ===
A_sym = A.T @ A
b_sym = A.T @ b

print("\n--- Simmetriklashtirilgan matritsa (A_bar = A^T * A) ---")
print(np.round(A_sym, 3))
```



```
# === 3. Cholesky (kvadrat ildizlar) usuli ===
def cholesky_decomposition(M):
    n = M.shape[0]
    S = np.zeros_like(M)
    for i in range(n):
        for j in range(i, n):
            if i == j:
                S[i, i] = np.sqrt(M[i, i] - np.sum(S[:i, i]**2))
            else:
                S[i, j] = (M[i, j] - np.sum(S[:i, i] * S[:i, j])) / S[i, i]
    return S

S = cholesky_decomposition(A_sym)
print("\n--- Cholesky (S) matritsa ---")
print(np.round(S, 4))

# === 4. Yechim topish ===
# S^T * Y = B_sym (oldinga yechish)
Y = np.zeros(n)
for i in range(n):
    Y[i] = (b_sym[i] - np.sum(S.T[i, :i] * Y[:i])) / S.T[i, i]

# S * X = Y (orqaga yechish)
X = np.zeros(n)
for i in reversed(range(n)):
    X[i] = (Y[i] - np.sum(S[i, i+1:] * X[i+1:])) / S[i, i]
```



```
print("\n--- Yechimlar (X) ---")
for i, val in enumerate(X, 1):
    print(f"x{i} = {val:.6f}")

# === 5. Determinant ===
det_A = np.linalg.det(A)
det_A_sym = np.linalg.det(A_sym)

print(f"\nA matritsa determinanti: det(A) = {det_A:.6f}")
print(f"Simmetrik matritsa determinanti: det(A^T*A) = {det_A_sym:.6f}")
```

Natija:

```
O'zgaruvchilar sonini kiriting (n): 3

A matritsa koeffitsiyentlarini kiriting (har bir satr alohida, elementlar orasiga bo'shliq qo'ying):
1-satr: 5 -7 8
2-satr: 8 -5 4
3-satr: -7 8 -5

Ozod hadlarni kiriting (B vektor):
B = 32 34 -7

--- Simmetriklashtirilgan matritsa (A_bar = A^T * A) ---
[[ 138. -131.  107.]
 [-131.  138. -116.]
 [ 107. -116.  105.]]

--- Cholesky (S) matritsa ---
[[ 11.7473 -11.1515  9.1084]
 [  0.      3.6939 -3.9058]
 [  0.      0.      2.6041]]

--- Yechimlar (X) ---
x1 = 6.000000
x2 = 10.000000
x3 = 9.000000

A matritsa determinanti: det(A) = 113.000000
Simmetrik matritsa determinanti: det(A^T*A) = 12769.000000
```

Yuqoridagi hisoblashlardan ko`rinadiki, yechimni topish uchun ancha vaqt sarflanadi. Lekin chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasini yechishning kvadrat ildizlar usulini qo'llshga doir dastur tuzib, shartlari bajarilgan chiziqli algebraik

tenglamalar sistemasini dasturdan foydalanib osongina ildizini topish mumkin.

Dasturni o`zgaruvchilar soni boshqacha bo`lgan chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasini misolga qo`llab ham aniq yechimni topish mumkin. Quyida o`zgaruvchilar soni 4 ta va 5 ta bo`lgan chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasining yecimini topamiz:

```
O'zgaruvchilar sonini kiriting (n): 5

A matritsa koeffitsiyentlarini kiriting (har bir satr alohida, elementlar o'asiga bo'shliq qo'ying):
1-satr: 1 1 1 1 1
2-satr: 2 0 3 1 1
3-satr: 1 2 2 3 4
4-satr: 3 1 1 2 3
5-satr: 4 3 4 2 2

O'zod hadlarni kiriting (B vektor):
B = 10 16 22 15 33

--- Simmetriklashtirilgan matritsa (A_bar = A^T * A) ---
[[31, 18, 20, 20, 24,]
 [18, 15, 18, 15, 18,]
 [20, 18, 31, 20, 23,]
 [20, 15, 20, 19, 24,]
 [24, 18, 23, 24, 31,]]

--- Cholesky (S) matritsa ---
[[ 5.5678  3.2329  5.0289  3.5921  4.3105]
 [ 0,      2.1327  0.8168  1.5882  1.9058]
 [ 0,      0,      2.2456  0.7842  -0.1042]
 [ 0,      0,      0,      1.8691  2.9527]
 [ 0,      0,      0,      0,      0.2400]]

--- Yechinlar (X) ---
x1 = 1.000000
x2 = 3.000000
x3 = 4.000000
x4 = 1.000000
x5 = 1.000000

A matritsa determinanti: det(A) = -12.000000
Simmetrik matritsa determinanti: det(A^T*A) = 144.000000
```



```
O'zgaruvchilar sonini kiriting (n): 4

A matritsa koeffitsiyentlarini kiriting (har bir satr alohida, elementlar orasiga bo'shliq qo'ying):
1-satr: 2 1 3 1
2-satr: 1 3 2 3
3-satr: 3 5 1 2
4-satr: 2 2 4 4

Ozod hadlarni kiriting (8 vektor):
B = 21 34 41 42

--- Simmetriklashtirilgan matritsa (A_bar = A^T * A) ---
[[18, 24, 19, 19.]
 [24, 39, 22, 28.]
 [19, 22, 30, 27.]
 [19, 28, 27, 30.]]

--- Cholesky (S) matritsa ---
[[ 4.2426  5.6569  4.4783  4.4783]
 [ 0.      2.6458 -1.2599  1.0079]
 [ 0.      0.      2.8909  2.8415]
 [ 0.      0.      0.      0.9245]]

--- Yechimlar (X) ---
x1 = 3.000000
x2 = 4.000000
x3 = 2.000000
x4 = 5.000000

A matritsa determinanti: det(A) = -30.000000
Simmetrik matritsa determinanti: det(A^T*A) = 900.000000
```

Ko`rinib turibdiki, chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasini yechishning kvadrat ildizlar usulini qo`llshda dasturlardan foydalanish natijani topish uchun ancha qulay. Shu bilan birga bunday izlanish davomida talaba ham matematikaga doir mavzuni o`rganadi, ham mavzuning dastur natijasini hosil qilish jarayonida dasturlashga doir bilimlarini oshiradi.

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